

Developing and validating an automated surveillance system for healthcare-associated *Clostridioides difficile* infection in Norway, 2019–2025

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Running title: DASH-CDI

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Table 1. Changelog.

Date	Version	Author(s)	Changes
22.05.2025	Version 0.1	ASD, TA, PRC, OEH, EH, NH, AI, RR, TCB, ALL, HMEV	First draft
12.08.2025	Version 1.0	All authors	First version
26.08.2025	Version 1.1	ASD, TA, PCR, OEH, NH, RR, TCB, ALL, HMEV	Specified details on the study sample and data extraction in the chart review.
23.06.2026	Version 1.2	ASD, TA, PCR, OEH, NH, ALL	Revised the sampling and data flow, changed running title and removed recurrent CDI

Abstract

Clostridioides difficile infection is a major cause of healthcare-associated diarrhoea and contributes substantially to the burden of healthcare-associated infections. Although largely preventable through infection prevention and control measures and antimicrobial stewardship, many surveillance systems cannot reliably distinguish healthcare-associated *C. difficile* infection from community-associated cases, limiting their value for targeted interventions. This study aims to develop and validate an automated surveillance system for healthcare-associated *C. difficile* infection in Norway by linking microbiological data from the Norwegian Surveillance System for Communicable Diseases with hospital admission data from the Norwegian Patient Registry. Cases will be classified using predefined operational definitions aligned with international standards. The classification algorithm will be validated against chart review data from four hospitals, and national epidemiological trends will be described for the period 2019–2025. Analyses will include incidence trends, patient demographics, strain characteristics including toxin profile and ribotype, length of hospital stay, re-admission, and all-cause mortality within 30 days after diagnosis. A retrospective cohort design will be applied, using routinely collected, pseudonymised and identifiable data.

Introduction

Clostridioides difficile infection (CDI) is the most common cause of healthcare-associated diarrhoea and a leading contributor to the burden of healthcare-associated infections (HAIs) [1–3]. CDIs can, however, be prevented through effective infection prevention and control (IPC) measures and prudent antimicrobial use, as highlighted by European guidelines and demonstrated in several studies [4–7]. Because of its preventability, the surveillance of healthcare-associated CDI (HA-CDI) is relevant from both a patient safety and a public health perspective [1,2,8]. While most national surveillance systems monitor CDI in general, distinguishing HA-CDI from community-associated cases may add important value [1]. First, it may enable the identification of actionable signals—such as local outbreaks or an increase in cases in specific facilities. Second, it may provide a meaningful indicator of the impact of IPC activities and antimicrobial stewardship programmes in healthcare institutions. Third, classifying CDI cases by healthcare association may also facilitate more appropriate benchmarking and trend interpretation, especially when changes in diagnostic practices or community prescribing may potentially obscure patterns relevant to hospital-based transmission.

In Denmark, CDI is included in the Healthcare Associated Infections Database (HAIBA), a national automated surveillance system for HAIs that draws on central health registries to classify cases as healthcare- or community-associated using predefined operational criteria [9,10]. To our knowledge, Denmark is the only country with a national-level automated surveillance of HA-CDI. However, there is a growing international trend towards automation of HAI surveillance across other agents, particularly within single hospitals or health systems. The PRAISE network (Providing a Roadmap for Automated Infection Surveillance in Europe) has developed high-level guidance for implementing automated surveillance, acknowledging that automation is usually most easily achieved locally due to the heterogeneity in how clinical data are stored on regional and national levels [11].

In Norway, the national surveillance of CDIs is performed using data found in the Norwegian Surveillance System for Communicable Diseases (MSIS). CDI first became a notifiable condition in 2012 but maintained patient anonymity. Since 2019 criteria have been updated to require that patient-identifiable reports are sent to MSIS from both laboratories and clinicians upon first detection [12,13]. This change also provided additional data for surveillance, however, did not include classification of healthcare association. In 2020, MSIS was expanded with the establishment of the MSIS-Laboratory database (MSIS-LabDB), which in real-time receives copies of test results from all medical microbiology laboratories in Norway. A planned automated surveillance system for CDI will be based on positive test results of CDI. By having a more comprehensive record of tests performed and their results, we will be able to provide a more accurate reconstruction of patient timelines. The advantage of replacing the existing system with an automated system that links data from different sources, such as the Norwegian Patient Registry (NPR), is believed to enable identification of healthcare-associated CDI infections, which is in line with the aim of the surveillance of CDI. However, an important difference, and perhaps drawback, of a surveillance system primarily based on laboratory data compared with the current surveillance is that cases of CDI that exclusively meet clinical criteria (i.e. pseudomembranous colitis or histopathological features of *C. difficile* detected by colonoscopy) will not be available in MSIS-LabDB data [14]. The existing mandatory notification of all CDI cases to MSIS will continue alongside the automated system, and although it cannot distinguish HA-CDI from CA-CDI, it does capture clinically diagnosed cases without microbiological confirmation; there are currently no plans to discontinue this reporting. A further limitation is that, as long as the municipal patient registry (*Kommunalt pasient- og brukerregister*, KPR) does not contain real-time information on residents of long-term care facilities, the HA definitions applied in the new system will remain incomplete, as exposure to care in such institutions cannot be reliably ascertained.

An internal evaluation of the surveillance system conducted at the Norwegian Institute of Public Health in 2022 for the 2019-2021 period identified challenges with the completeness of manually reported variables and regional variation in reporting quality. The data were presented at the ESCAIDE conference in 2022 [15]. While the system was deemed to be broadly useful, it lacked the capacity to distinguish between HA- and community-associated CDI (CA-CDI), limiting its utility for issuing recommendations and IPC. At the same time, improvements to surveillance systems must consider the need to reduce – not increase – the reporting burden on clinical staff. This project builds on the findings of that evaluation by developing an automated system for classifying CDI cases as HA-CDI or CA-CDI, using linked microbiological and hospital admission data. The classification algorithm will be validated against chart review data from four hospitals. In addition, the project will provide a national description of the CDI epidemiology in Norway from 2019 to 2025, including incidence trends, a selection of clinical outcomes, strain distribution (toxin and ribotype), and patient characteristics.

Study aim and objectives

Aim

To develop and validate an automated surveillance system for classifying CDI cases in Norway as HA-CDI or CA-CDI, and describe the national epidemiology of CDI from 2019 to 2025.

Objectives

- Develop an algorithm that classifies CDI as HA-CDI or CA-CDI using linked microbiological laboratory investigations and hospital admission data.
- Validate the algorithm against chart review data from four hospitals.
- Describe national HA-CDI and CA-CDI epidemiology and clinical outcomes from 2019 to 2025, including
 - Epidemiology: incidence trends, strain distribution, toxin profiles, and ribotypes/sequence types, from 2019 to 2025.
 - Outcome: length of stay post diagnosis, re-admission and mortality.

Materials and methods

This is a retrospective, observational study applying a cohort study design using routinely collected national microbiological and hospital data in national registries.

CDI case definition in the MSIS register

In the current notification criteria in the MSIS register, a case of CDI is defined as a person aged ≥ 2 years who meets at least one of the following criteria, and where no previous CDI case has been reported for the same individual within the preceding 8 weeks:

1. Loose stools (diarrhoea) or toxic megacolon **and** a positive laboratory test for *C. difficile* toxin A and/or toxin B in stool, **or** detection of toxin-producing *C. difficile* in stool by culture or other methods (e.g. detection of toxin A or toxin B gene).
2. Pseudomembranous colitis demonstrated by colonoscopy.
3. Histopathological evidence of CDI in the colon (with or without diarrhoea) from a sample obtained during colonoscopy, colectomy, or autopsy.

Positive CDI tests in MSIS-LabDB

When defining positive laboratory tests in the MSIS-LabDB, tests will be considered in a hierarchy to distinguish active toxin production from potential for toxin production, to prioritise between samples within the episode period. The hierarchy will prioritise methods with higher specificity for active infection:

1. Combined algorithms detecting both glutamate dehydrogenase (GDH) and toxin (e.g. GDH EIA followed by toxin EIA or NAAT).
2. Toxin A/B enzyme immunoassay (EIA), either alone or as confirmatory step after screening.
3. Nucleic acid amplification tests (NAAT) alone, indicating potential for toxin production.
4. Toxigenic culture and cytotoxicity assay, where available.

Data sources

This study will use two distinct datasets, Dataset 1 (Figure 1) and Dataset 2 (Figure 2).

Dataset 1 is a national cohort consisting of pseudonymised individual-level data from the MSIS register, linked to NPR, covering all cases of CDI over the study period between 1 January 2019 and 31 December 2025. The MSIS case data will be linked to NPR, which contains data on all hospital admissions and discharges in Norway, using a pseudonymised version of the unique personal identification number assigned to all Norwegian residents. For each patient, the NPR will provide dates and times of admission and discharge for all inpatient stays in the somatic, specialist healthcare. Where possible, cases will be doubly identified in the MSIS register and MSIS-LabDB, with supplementary analyses describing any potential discrepancies.

Figure 1. Data sources and cohort construction. From the time data becomes available in MSIS-LabDB, data from MSIS register will continue to be used to supplement certain variables.

Dataset 2 is a selection of directly identifiable data. The selection will be based on MSIS data. It is desirable to capture individuals who were hospitalised at least at one of the four hospitals selected to participate in the chart review study and with a confirmed CDI regardless of where it was first detected. Approximately one third of CDI cases are not detected in hospitals [16]. MSIS will define a sample of 200 patients per hospital. The selection will be based on positive test results and will start from 31 December 2025 and proceeding retrospectively until 200 patients are identified. A positive test will be considered relevant when performed at one of the microbiological laboratories located at the four hospitals or hospital trusts included in the study. Once the patients are identified, MSIS will collect all their positive samples spanning the study period 90 days prior and send the corresponding sample dates to NPR. NPR will identify those who were inpatients at sampling time and return every record of hospital stays for these patients within ± 90 days of the earliest positive sample date provided by MSIS. The NPR data will be sent back to MSIS whom will then split the data into two study files: the first, containing personal identification numbers, sample dates, and a project identifier, which will be securely distributed to the validation hospitals or hospital trusts using Sikt FileSender (Feide login); the second, containing the project identifier, sample dates, all positive CDI samples, regardless of which laboratory performed the analysis, within ± 90 days of the sample date added to the dataset by MSIS, and all NPR records within ± 90 days, will be sent to the project team internally at the Norwegian Institute of Public Health for algorithmic classification. The hospitals will validate the corresponding clinical information from their electronic health records, create a copy without personal identifiers, and deliver their findings in pseudonymised form to the project team at the Norwegian Institute of Public Health.

To evaluate the degree of agreement between the algorithm's findings and the chart review, the project team will require the following data for patients in the validation sub cohort: all positive CDI samples within ± 90 days of the index sample date; hospital admission and discharge dates for the period 90 days before and after the defining positive microbiological sample; date of death or readmission within 30 days after the sample date; as well as age and sex.

Figure 2. Data sources and cohort construction for dataset 2.

The four hospitals (three hospitals and one hospital trust) selected for the validation study are all located within the South-Eastern Norway Regional Health Authority and represent different levels of the specialist healthcare system. Oslo University Hospital (OUS) is Norway's largest hospital trust and provides a wide range of national and regional specialist services. Akershus University Hospital, Nordbyhagen location (Ahus) is Norway's largest acute care hospital serving one of the country's fastest growing populations. Østfold Hospital Kalnes is a modern regional hospital covering the population of Østfold County, while Bærum Hospital is a local hospital within the Vestre Viken Hospital Trust. All four hospitals have recently had a particular focus on *C. difficile* surveillance,

making them well suited for validation activities with established routines. As an indication of relative size, OUS reported more than 25,000 full-time equivalent (FTE) staff in 2024, compared with approximately 11,000 at Ahus, 5,000 at Østfold Hospital, and 2,300 at Bærum hospital, as per each hospital's yearly reports. The inclusion of hospitals spanning national, regional, and local functions is intended to ensure that the validation reflects a range of patient populations and hospitalisation patterns, and to support assessment of the algorithm's performance across diverse clinical settings, but hospitals that were geographically close to each other was prioritised to facilitate the review process.

Table 2. Variable list.

Variable	Role	Source	Values / Categories
Pseudonymised personal identification number	Linkage key	MSIS	Personal ID (pseudonymised for national data, directly identifiable for the selection)
Sample date	Exposure	MSIS	Date
Admission date	Exposure	NPR	Date and time
Discharge date	Exposure	NPR	Date and time
Hospital-/community-onset and -association classification, 4 categories	Main outcome	Derived from MSIS + NPR	1. HOHA 2. COHA 3. COIA 4. CA
Onset and association classification, 2 categories	Main outcome	Derived from MSIS + NPR	HA-CDI or CA-CDI
Chart review classification	Validation outcome	Hospital records	HA-CDI or CA-CDI, only for Dataset 2
<i>C. difficile</i> identification	Epidemiological outcome	MSIS	Positive <i>C. difficile</i> test, should be 1 for everyone
Toxin profile	Epidemiological outcome	MSIS	Type of toxin if specified
Toxin detection method	Epidemiological outcome	MSIS	Methods (e.g., EIA, NAAT, etc.)
Ribotype	Epidemiological outcome	MSIS	Ribotype number or unknown
Length of stay post diagnosis	Clinical outcome	MSIS + NPR	Days (continuous)
Re-admission	Clinical outcome	NPR	Yes or no
Mortality	Clinical outcome	NPR	Yes or no
Healthcare-association documented in chart	Covariate	Chart review	Yes or no, only for Dataset 2
Age	Covariate	NPR/MSIS	Years (continuous or grouped)
Sex	Covariate	NPR/MSIS	Male, Female
Hospital location	Covariate	NPR	County or health region
Hospital name	Covariate	NPR/MSIS	Hospital name or code
Hospital department	Covariate	NPR	Hospital department name

Classification of onset and association (Dataset 1 and 2)

Each CDI case will be classified according to onset and healthcare association, using definitions aligned with current ECDC surveillance standards and adapted for automated classification in the NoHAI system [14]:

1. **Hospital-onset healthcare-associated CDI (HOHA-CDI):** Sample collected on day 3 or later after hospital admission, or within 2 days after discharge from the same admission (date of admission is day 1).
2. **Community-onset healthcare-associated CDI (COHA-CDI):** Sample collected in the community or on day 1–2 of admission, with an inpatient stay in the previous 28 days (outpatient visits excluded). (Note: definitions usually also count stays in long term care facilities, but this is information still unavailable to FHI.)
3. **Community-onset indeterminate association (COIA):** Sample collected in the community or on day 1–2 of admission, with inpatient discharge 4–12 weeks (29–84 days) before sampling.
4. **Community-associated CDI (CA-CDI):** Sample collected in the community or on day 1–2 of admission, with no inpatient discharge in the previous 12 weeks (84 days).

A binary version of this variable will also be used, where category 1 and 2 will be considered HA-CDI and category 3 and 4 will be considered community-associated.

All timestamps are converted to dates and only calendar days are considered.

Validation of association (Dataset 2)

To evaluate the performance of the algorithm, validation will be conducted using chart review data from four hospitals. The hospitals will review CDI cases using clinical records to classify onset and association independent of the algorithm, following the clinical classification from the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC), including local adaptations if any [14]. In other words, the clinical review may use slightly different criteria than the automated algorithm, and this is intentional. The aim of the validation is to assess how well the algorithm reproduces clinical judgement based on ECDC definitions, not simply whether the data recorded in registries match what is stored in electronic health records. Furthermore, as hospitals do not have information on patients who has not been admitted to their hospitals, only cases with a recent history in the specific hospital can be reviewed. In addition, hospitals will record information on whether the HA-/CA-status of the CDI was documented or not in the patient chart, along with which information was used to classify the case as HA or CA (Appendix 3). The classification output from the automated algorithm will be compared with the chart review as a reference standard to estimate sensitivity, specificity, and predictive values.

Validation results will be summarised in a diagnostic 2×2 table comprising of true positives (TP), false positives (FP), true negatives (TN), and false negatives (FN), comparing the classification from the automated algorithm with that from chart review. Sensitivity and specificity will be reported with 95% confidence intervals. A sample size is calculated using Buderer's method for diagnostic accuracy studies [17,18]:

For sensitivity, the required number with the disease $(TP + FN)$ is

$$TP + FN = \frac{Z^2_{\alpha/2} * SN(1 - SN)}{W^2}$$

where $Z^2_{\alpha/2}$ is the standard normal value for the desired confidence level, α is the Type I error rate, W is the maximum acceptable total width of the confidence interval, and SN is the expected sensitivity. The total sample size needed is then

$$N_1 = \frac{TP + FN}{P}$$

where $TP + FN$ is the number of diseased, which is scaled up by dividing on the expected prevalence P to arrive at the total sensitivity-based sample size N_1 . The same logic can be applied to calculate the total specificity-based sample size N_2 by dividing the number without the disease by the inverse of the expected prevalence. The total sample size needed is then the larger of the two.

As no Norwegian prevalence estimates of HA-CDI are available, we draw on recent European surveillance reports. The most recent UK Health Security Agency annual report (2023–2024) reports a proportion of about 65%, while the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) surveillance report (2018–2020) reports about 60% [19,20]. Although we have no direct precedent for the sensitivity of this algorithm, both the automated system and the chart reviews will classify cases using ECDC definitions, and sensitivity is therefore expected to be high, reflecting agreement between the two approaches. Specificity is assumed to be 99%, reflecting that false positives are expected to be very rare. We further assume a two-sided 95% confidence level, a two-sided confidence interval width of 5 percentage points, and no dropouts. Table 3 shows the required sample sizes for different combinations of prevalence and sensitivity.

Table 3. Sample size calculation of the validation analysis using Buderer's method for diagnostic accuracy studies.

		Sensitivity					
		90%	92%	94%	96%	98%	99.9%
Prevalence	50%	277	227	174	119	61	31
	55%	252	206	158	108	55	34
	60%	231	189	145	99	51	39
	65%	213	174	134	91	47	44
	70%	198	162	124	85	51	51
	75%	185	151	116	79	61	61

The table shows that at higher numbers of expected sensitivity and prevalence, the specificity-based sample size needed is the larger of the two. More importantly, it shows that generally speaking, a low sample size is needed to achieve sufficient statistical power. As such, each hospital will review at least 100 CDI cases, giving a total sample size of 400, to allow for a margin of error and observed values out of the range covered by the table.

Epidemiological and clinical outcomes (Dataset 1 and 2)

The following clinical outcomes will be defined in both Dataset 1 and 2. Length of stay post-diagnosis will be calculated as the number of days from the date of the first positive CDI test in the index episode to the date of discharge from the same admission. Re-admission will be defined as any new inpatient admission regardless of diagnosis in NPR within 30 days of discharge from the admission during which the index episode was diagnosed. Mortality will include all-cause deaths occurring at any point within 30 days after CDI diagnosis, as recorded in NPR (enriched from the Population Registry). Ribotype will be recorded where reported.

Statistical analyses (Dataset 1 and 2)

In addition to the tables calculating the diagnostic performance of the algorithm in Dataset 2, the study will provide a national description of CDI epidemiology in Norway between 2019 and 2025 using Dataset 1. Descriptive statistics will include the annual number of CDI cases, incidence rates by month and year, and proportions classified as HA- or CA-CDI, summarised in tables or figures as appropriate. Patient characteristics of sex and age will be described, both continuously and stratified by age group (e.g. 2–19, 20–39, 40–59, 60–79, 80+ years). For cases with known genomic characteristics such as toxin type or ribotype, distributions will be presented separately for HA- and CA-CDI. Where ribotype data are missing, this will be noted and proportions calculated from available data. Additional stratified figures (e.g. incidence by age group and year) may be included if patterns suggest age-related trends.

The epidemiological outcomes of toxin profile, toxin detection method, and ribotype will be described overall and stratified by HA- and CA-CDI. Median and interquartile range of length of stay post-diagnosis will be calculated for hospitalised patients, with stratification by HA- and CA-CDI. Re-admission rates within 30 days will be reported as proportions with corresponding 95% confidence intervals. Mortality will be described as the proportion of all-cause deaths within 30 days after CDI diagnosis, overall and stratified by epidemiological category and age group.

Sensitivity analyses will be performed using increasingly restrictive case definitions based on the laboratory hierarchy to assess the impact of including cases identified by less specific methods (e.g. NAAT alone) on incidence estimates and classification of healthcare association.

All analyses will be performed using R (version $\geq 4.3.0$), and results will be reported in line with STROBE guidelines for observational studies [21,22].

Limitations

These studies rely on routinely collected registry data, meaning information transferred from laboratories and hospitals to central databases for surveillance. By design, such data lack “deep” clinical detail, for example symptoms, vital signs, or biochemistry. In the context of *C. difficile*, markers such as fever, C-reactive protein, or procalcitonin could in principle contribute to distinguishing colonisation from infection, but they are not available in the registries we use. Registry data are also less granular than clinical records, often recorded on the level of calendar days rather than hours, which further limits clinical interpretation. Although this is an inherent feature of automated surveillance, it may lead to differences between how cases and episodes are defined in registers compared to clinical practice or specifically designed surveillance systems based on manual reporting.

Data on hospital antibiotic exposure are not available at the individual level, as the Norwegian Prescription Database is not yet prepared to deliver person-level data from hospitals for research. This limits our ability to assess known risk factors or stratify by prior antibiotic use.

Strain data such as ribotype and toxin type in MSIS are mainly incomplete since many laboratories do not culture strains, so ribotyping/sequence type is not possible. Also, laboratories often do not report on which toxin/toxin gene is detected. As a result, some analyses will rely on a subset of cases, and representativeness may be limited. As it stands now, a new and automated surveillance system of HA-CDI will have to rely solely on microbiological results and cannot exclude cases that lack clinical symptoms.

We are unable to estimate the outcome recurrent CDI (rCDI), as its definition requires a negative test between positive tests, and we are currently unable to link negative test results to NPR data.

Project management

Data processing and ethical approvals

This project uses two distinct datasets, each with a separate legal basis for data processing.

For the national cohort (Dataset 1), all data are pseudonymised and consist of indirectly identifiable personal health information from MSIS and NPR. This data is processed as part of a quality assurance study, which means it is exempt from approval from the Regional Committees for Medical and Health Research Ethics (REK). The status as a quality assurance study has been confirmed by the Norwegian Directorate of Health (Helsedirektoratet) and MSIS who both granted exemptions from the duty of confidentiality under §19b of the Health Registry Act. In addition, a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) has been approved by the internal Data Protection Officer (Personvernombudet, PVO) at the Norwegian Institute of Public Health. Additionally, the supplementary legal basis for data processing is the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) Article 6(1)(e), and Article 9(2)(i).

For the chart review dataset (Dataset 2), the data are directly identifiable and include personal identification numbers used to retrieve patient records from selected hospitals. REK has determined that their approval is not required, and the project will apply to Health Data Service (Helsedataservice) for permission to process data from health registries. Health Data Service will request an assessment from the Directorate of Health who will, if appropriate, grant dispensation from confidentiality. Where hospital medical records are accessed, the PVO or research department at the individual hospitals will be consulted and involved in the processing assessment, and recommend the performance of the study if they deem it appropriate. The internal PVO at the Norwegian Institute of Public Health will be consulted for review and guidance on internal compliance prior to initiating data collection for Dataset 2, including whether data processing agreements are necessary to sign with the hospitals.

All data will be processed and stored within the secure zone at the Norwegian Institute of Public Health, approved for handling sensitive health data. Personal identification numbers are included for a subset of cases to enable medical record validation, while national registry data are pseudonymised using encrypted identifiers. Identification of participants will be restricted to designated staff, who follow the internal routines for confidentiality and handling of health data at the Norwegian Institute of Public Health. All personnel with access to identifiable data are trained in data protection and bound by confidentiality agreements. Data quality will be ensured through registry-based validation routines and linkage checks. Only anonymous (aggregate) data will be published, with no individual-level data disclosed. The downsides and data integrity risks are considered low for all participants and outweighed by the benefits for both patients and society.

Project organisation

Table 4. Project participants and their respective responsibilities.

Author	Affiliation	Responsibility
Anders Skyrud Danielsen	Norwegian Institute of Public Health	Project coordination, study design, data curation, data analysis, data interpretation, drafting manuscript, revising manuscript

Torunn Alberg	Norwegian Institute of Public Health	Project coordination, study design, data interpretation, drafting manuscript, revising manuscript
Pascale-Renée Cyr	Norwegian Institute of Public Health	Study design, data extraction, data processing, data interpretation, revising manuscript
Othilde Elise Håvelsrud	Norwegian Institute of Public Health	Study design, data extraction, data processing, data interpretation, revising manuscript
Eyvind Helland	Norwegian Institute of Public Health	Data extraction, data processing, data interpretation, revising manuscript
Nina Handal	Norwegian Institute of Public Health	Data interpretation, revising manuscript
André Ingebretsen	Oslo University Hospital	Data interpretation, revising manuscript
Ragnhild Raastad	Norwegian Institute of Public Health	Data interpretation, revising manuscript
Thale Cathrine Berg	Norwegian Institute of Public Health	Data interpretation, revising manuscript
Astrid Louise Løvlie	Norwegian Institute of Public Health	Data interpretation, revising manuscript
Elisabeth Dietz	University of Oxford	Data interpretation, revising manuscript
Astri Lervik Larsen	Østfold Hospital	Data curation, data analysis, data interpretation, revising manuscript
Kirsten Midttun Gravningen	Akershus University Hospital	Data curation, data analysis, data interpretation, revising manuscript
Astrid Halvorsen Schreiner	Akershus University Hospital	Data curation, data analysis, data interpretation, revising manuscript
Lars Magnus Rutger Andersson	Oslo University Hospital	Data curation, data analysis, data interpretation, revising manuscript
Carola Grub	Oslo University Hospital	Data curation, data analysis, data interpretation, revising manuscript
Mette Walberg	Vestre Viken Hospital Trust	Data curation, data analysis, data interpretation, revising manuscript
Ellen Brustad	Vestre Viken Hospital Trust	Data curation, data analysis, data interpretation, revising manuscript
Astrid Louise Wester	Vestre Viken Hospital Trust	Data curation, data analysis, data interpretation, revising manuscript
David Eyre	University of Oxford	Data interpretation, revising manuscript
Hanne-Merete Eriksen-Volle	Norwegian Institute of Public Health	Project administration, study design, data curation, data analysis, data interpretation, drafting manuscript, revising manuscript

Timeline

Table 5. GANTT chart.

Task	2025								2026												2027								
	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep
Finalise protocol, incl. data flow	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█																
Apply for ethical approvals (REK, PVO, HDS (Hdir))			█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█													
Invite hospitals and coordinate access	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█												
Receive and process registry data					█	█	█	█									█	█	█										
Conduct chart reviews					█	█	█	█										█	█	█	█	█	█	█					
Analyse data					█	█	█	█															█	█	█				
Write manuscript					█	█	█	█																█	█	█	█	█	█

Dissemination

A manuscript of this analysis will be sent to one of three peer-reviewed medical journals, in the following prioritised order:

1. Eurosurveillance
2. Journal of Hospital Infection
3. Antimicrobial Resistance and Infection Control

References

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Appendix

Appendix 1: Clinical criteria for healthcare-associated classification
Criteria for the classification of CDI as HA-CDI or CA-CDI according to ECDC.

CDI case origin

The origin of a CDI case can be healthcare-associated, community-associated or unknown.

Figure 1. Designation of CDI cases as healthcare-associated or community-associated based on location and time of onset of symptoms.

Healthcare-associated CDI (HA CDI) is defined as a case of CDI with onset of symptoms:

- on day three or later, following admission to a healthcare facility on day one,
OR
- in the community within four weeks of discharge from a healthcare facility (including the current hospital or a previous stay in any other healthcare facility).

Community-associated CDI (CA CDI) is defined as a case of CDI with onset of symptoms:

- outside of healthcare facilities
AND without discharge from a healthcare facility within the previous 12 weeks,
OR
- on the day of admission to a healthcare facility or on the following day
AND not resident in a healthcare facility within the previous 12 weeks.

Unknown association: the CDI case was discharged from a healthcare facility 4–12 weeks before the onset of symptoms.

Appendix 2: Data flow and analysis process in NoHAI (flowchart diagram)

Appendix 3: Validation form

<i>Sett kryss i feltet som stemmer for det aktuelle tilfellet</i>										
	Klassifikasjon	Kriterier møtt			Informasjon brukt					
Pasient	Helsetjenesteassosiert	Dag ≥3 etter innleggelse (innleggelsesdag er dag 1)	Tidligere sykehusopphold* <4 uker fra prøvedato	Annet opphold i helseinstitusjon (annet sykehus eller sykehjem, notér hvilke) <4 uker siden	Datofelter i EPJ	Datofelter i lab-applikasjon	Datofelter i kjernejournal	Legenotater/epikriser i løpende journal	Sykepleiernotater i løpende journal	Annet/kommentar [fritekst]
Pasient 1										
Pasient 2										
Pasient 3										
Pasient 4										
Pasient 5										

*Gjelder også andre sykehus